

► **VVM Deliverable 11**

Final Quality Criteria and Final Methodology

Version 1.0

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1 Introduction

1.1 Executive summary

Developing an Automated Driving System (ADS) is a complex task involving many stakeholders from different domains. Taking up this challenge, the VV Methods project (VVM) <https://www.vvm-projekt.de/en/> has developed a general methodology that is proposed as a new common basis to develop and ensure the safety of future Automated Driving Systems (ADS). The methodology enables the analysis, monitoring and control of the risk resulting from operating the ADS in its desired Operational Domain¹ for driver, passengers and other traffic participants during the development to ensure that the result maintains an acceptable level of risk. The methodological framework proposed by VVM also integrates key aspects needed to provide evidence of this in a safety case. The framework is explicitly designed for industrial application. It builds on the PEGASUS method (<https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/en/>) for scenario-based testing and addresses the challenges of operating an ADS in and coping with the complexity of urban traffic.

The main overall approach of the VVM methodology is represented in Figure 1. It combines argumentation concepts (pink) establishing the coverage of the operational design domain (ODD) and the operational domain (OD) by scenarios with an assurance framework (light blue) defining the processes and means to develop the ADS for that ODD within the OD. While the argumentation concepts are not fully formalized, the assurance framework is based on formal formats and tool-based procedures, in particular for verification and validation tasks, that can be directly integrated into industrial practice.

The project's approach and achievements can be summarized in the following theses.

- The safety of complex automated driving systems can only be established by integrating a wide range of technical and social perspectives. As a key element, VVM proposes an approach that brings these perspectives together.
- A system can be trusted only if we are convinced that it is safe. The safety argument is a central concern of the VVM methodology. The VVM approach now enables to convincingly prove the safety of an automated driving system.
- A development process implementing the VVM methodology will provide the basis for verifying the safety of automated vehicles. All OEMs adopting the methodology would use the same structures for the verification and validation of automated driving systems in urban areas. This may lead to industry-wide standards that could make road traffic even safer for all road users.

¹ The term "Operational Domain" is equivalently used to the term "Target Operational Domain" according to ISO 34503.

Figure 1: Overall VVM design space: Argumentation concept and assurance framework

This positioning paper starts with an introduction and a summary of general AD safety assurance challenges, and the top goals chosen by VVM to address these challenges in Chapter 1.

Chapter 2 presents and discusses the main VVM position towards a central VVM thesis statement and four subtheses with related argumentations, see Figure 2. Overall VVM design space: Argumentation concept and assurance framework. These subtheses capture the relation between the identified challenges and the chosen top goals. They delineate the solution space and summarize how the VVM methodology addresses the challenges. Future research and development activities, which further develop and complement the project results, can also orient themselves within this framework.

Figure 2: VVM general thesis statement and according subtheses

In Chapter 3 the main VVM result is presented by building up a tangible solution space based on the theses and their supporting argumentation and contrasted by the given challenges and top goals of the project. This positioning paper closes with an overview of remaining research needs in Chapter 5, supplemented by recommendations on how scenario-based testing methodologies can be applied.

1.2 Status VV Methods scenario-based safety assurance

Scenario-based testing methodologies for demonstrating the safety of ADS, the associated need for coherent measurement values, formats, procedures, and parameter ranges, as well as the necessary shift of the test space into simulation environments (or virtual environments), are the focus of many global research and development initiatives. The crucial factors behind this are the required reduction of the unlimited parameter space associated with the challenges of development, test and type approval of an ADS functionalities as well as with the latest regulations in the member states of the European Union for a certain Operating Domain (OD).

These initiatives from research, industry, test design, standardization, regulation, and large-scale deployment share a common center: scenario-based development and validation procedures and the associated shift of the design and test space into simulation-based methods.

The VV Methods (<https://www.vvm-projekt.de/en/>) project provides fundamental and scalable approaches towards a comprehensive overall methodology for scenario-based safety verification and validation in automated driving.

VVM in combination with the SET Level project (<https://setlevel.de/>) as part of the PEGASUS project family have developed an overall argumentation structure for the safety verification and validation of ADS using design and implementation methods of scenario-based approaches.

In addition to the systematical derivation of initial test situations through the definition of criticalities and the OD-describing ontologies, the VVM overall approach provides a methodical and technically applicable structure enabling an overall safety argumentation. The overall approach at the beginning was to shift the common V-model structure and its according development and validation elements and processes as much as possible into simulation-based methods in order to reduce work on physical components and full prototypes to a manageable minimum. Nevertheless, physical testing and data capturing from the real-world will always remain a key part of the development and validation process.

VV Methods has defined the overall methodology based on the PEGASUS project and is aligned with corresponding standardization initiatives. The integrated SET Level project has provided the appropriate simulation architecture with which individual components such as sensor models or driving functions can be tested so that they can then be subjected to safety verification in accordance with regulations.

The intended area of application is urban driving, including the typical complex conditions that occur there. Methodologies for formal scenario descriptions, the optimization of parameter spaces as well as parameter sampling methods and the integration of real data collected in the field into the simulation-based verification are at the heart of both projects.

VVM and SET Level propose approaches to map the infinite parameter space (complex traffic scenarios are made efficiently manageable by examining the interdependencies) into a still large but finite set of specific logical scenarios with certain properties, covering representatively the Operational Design Domain (ODD). Furthermore, tests can be performed both on the system and on subsystem level. In this context, real testing is shifted to simulative methods wherever possible, which leads to an increase in cost and time efficiency. Also, such simulative approaches, ranging from model/software-in-the-loop to hardware- and even prototype/vehicle-in-the-loop methods, enable development and validation work that would not be accessible for physical testing for reasons of sheer size of the parameter variation or safety implications. To demonstrate the feasibility, a complete test chain from model-in-the-loop to test bench (Hardware-in-the-Loop) to real driving is set up as an example. With regard to industrialization, working on the proof of safety becomes also part of the development process via systematic approaches (and a "design for testability"). This is ensured by binding and connecting coherent interfaces and processes to industrial automotive processes.

The core of both projects is developing a development and validation structure for safe automated driving, including the necessary methods for parameter variation, so that the test coverage derived from these results in a representative number of simulatable scenarios, variations and eventualities, complemented by physical testing. Both VVM and SET Level are purely pre-competitive R&D projects funded by the German Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action. In addition to the methodological approaches, the focus is also on the operational concretization of test scenarios, the structuring of the databases, the use of open definitions and tools as well as example implementation of results of the two interlinked projects.

The work within VVM and SET Level was performed in close interaction with worldwide partner initiatives and projects as well as standardization bodies, through cooperation and joint expert workshops of the PEGASUS family. A unique point of VVM and SET Level projects was to develop an overall methodology covering both sides of the V-model and spanning over many abstraction layers from pure model-in-the-loop simulation to real-world driving and data capturing, as well as addressing the complexities of driving in an urban environment for AD systems

1.3 VVM goals, challenges and solution space

At the very beginning of the VVM project, four top goals were defined as guiding and target corridors for all levels of complexity within VVM (see Figure 3). These goals set out the requirement to reduce the unlimited test space for automated driving to a manageable and balanced finite number and to shift test efforts as much as possible into a means of virtual validation and assessment by simulation. Beside the technological challenges, the need to include boundary conditions such as rules, laws or the social definition of safety into the test space in a formalizing way was shaping these top goals as well.

The systematic decomposition of the OD was chosen as on one access instrument to solve this challenge as defined by top **goal 1 "Systematic control of test space"**. The systematic decomposition of OD incorporating relevant hazardous phenomena, involvement of traffic-law perspective and the identification and description of a target behavior within the ODD were the main drafting lines for the argumentation concept. Applying this approach means reducing the unlimited options in reality and parameters to an infinite and practicable size. **Goal 2** - the demand for

"**Consistent Interfaces**" emphasizes the need to break down the various definition and process steps of the argumentation into technically applicable test and verification procedures. The argumentation and verification chain is thus subjected to a real feasibility test. Using virtual components and parameter spaces associated with **goal 3** "Shift to simulation", the simulation space is enhanced with more degrees of freedom to integrate further virtual elements and opportunities to mix them with real artefact data to perform an almost unlimited range of test space

Goal 4 "Explainable safety" means the constant requirement to all process steps of the argumentation being explainable, traceable and consistent to relevant stakeholders. One main challenge here is that an enormous number/variety of input variables must be taken into account and that some of these are of a non-technical, non-formal nature, but ultimately the technical proof must be very well explainable and must also be able to be carried out according to social criteria.

Figure 3: VV Methods management top goals of project

In addition to these top goals at management level, the following challenges were decisive for the development of the VVM overall method. These challenges are also valid beyond VVM and can significantly define future projects for the applied proof of safety.

The deployment of ADS can be accelerated by linking these 6 thematic challenge corridors with the relevant stakeholders under the presence of growing and open innovative data- and scenario ecosystems.

These challenges (see Table 1) are the result of both project-internal investigations as well as the result of various liaisons between VVM and experts and stakeholders worldwide.

Table 1: Challenges as accompanying framework for the thematic VVM project corridors

Challenge	Details
C1 We have to develop a definition of safety and safe systems on the road	<p>The society expects just safety, thus safety and generally compliance must be argued to the stakeholders of society before introduction. The absence of unreasonable risk is argued via several societal claims – following laws and standards. Using quantified risk helps threefold: for defining design tagged values, for a robust safety argumentation, and for comprehensible approval decisions. The expectation of society is a safety argumentation including quantification of risk. The expectation of society is a safety argumentation including quantification of risk.</p>
C2 ODD-decomposition by scenarios and argumentation of ODD-coverage are key to master open world	<p>The argumentation of a representative ODD-coverage by specifically designed logical scenarios is the key for a systematic control of the development and validation space (main result VVM), thus the argumentation of a sufficient ODD-coverage using the VVM ODD meta model is essential for the overall VVM method</p> <p>The VVM ODD meta model is in that sense an appropriate and sufficient model of the ODD by introducing a structured methodology for the reality abstraction by using independent logical scenarios with special properties, the so-called base scenarios.</p>
C3 Safety argumentation and development process have to correspond	<p>Safety argumentation and development process have to correspond in all layers and in the whole complexity.</p> <p>In order to master this complexity, the Argumentation, Design and V&V should start with an abstract perspective i.e. using capabilities and target behavior of the system and should be followed by formal decomposition to prove the integrity and safety of sub-systems. Legacy quality processes must consider metrics of formal decomposition along the argumentation.</p>
C4 Virtualization is mandatory	<p>Despite all systematic structuring, the challenge for systems operating in an open context imposes a tremendous demand of tests and data. Virtualization of models and data on all relevant layers is mandatory. Of course, there is a significant number of residual real-world tests remaining for completion.</p>

C5	Tools and Formats need to be coherent and support argumentation	<p>Seamless tool chains from simulation to proof-in-field should be based on open specifications, open (data)-formats as i.e. ontologies should support ODD-coverage. Interfaces should support quality metrics of technical systems and sub-systems.</p> <p>Common effort is needed to develop standardized formats and metrics for the complete toolchain including a proof-of-concept implementation.</p>
C6	Continuous integration between verification and validation ecosystems has to be enabled	<p>Data-driven approaches to continuously feed growing data and scenario pools into industrial useable and evolving tool chains are a key (and required) success factor to enhance legacy safety case chains with future data and adapted scenarios.</p> <p>The development and application of qualifiable, implementable and certifiable processes and tools require systematic approaches to accessibility and interoperability, such as those being developed by new approaches in the open data / open source community.</p>

2 The VV Methods position by theses and argumentation

Once the problem space and derived objectives have been clearly identified, the next step is to draw up a list of theses and an argument describing why a solution space can be mapped to the problem space on the basis of the theses. The following 4 central theses are set against the 6 challenges whereby the respective theses and their arguments address one or more challenges.

Thesis Statement

VVM provides a new method which proves testing and development processes for safe operation of level 4 automated driving systems in an urban context for a general accepted risk acceptance

Figure 4: General thesis statement

With the VVM general method, we ensure that the target behavior of the ADS and its architecture is designed in such a way that systematic hazards and triggering events are addressed. Addressing safety measures were chosen in such a way that they reduce risk to an acceptable level.

With the VVM overall method, we ensure that the ADS to be developed is safe in such a way that it operates in its ODD with an acceptable risk.

2.1 Subthesis 1 – Consistent usage of an ODD Metamodel Approach

Pegasus has anchored the role of simulation for automated driving system manufacturers through scenario-based testing. The integration of the overall system and the integration of the ADS into the vehicle are essentially verified on digital platforms based on simulation methods. The evidence resulting from simulations is confirmed by a few coordinated tests performed on proving grounds as well as in real world driving. In the established ADS development process in the automotive industry, the 6-layer scenario model for scenario-based testing found in PEGASUS was one of several scenario models used alternatively and in parallel for problem/domain analysis, behavior specification, and architecture design. The existing model diversity is the starting point for VVM's new ODD metamodel approach.

VVM extends this with a holistic view of the development process and integrates elements included in current standards, for example from FUSA and SOTIF.

The metamodel approach for the ODD (OMA) established in VVM supports the requirement for decomposition: on the modeling level (functional, logical, ...), on the scenario level, on the level of the 6-layer and on the level of the chosen descriptive parameters. The demand for decomposition capability results from different requirements in the development process, such as hazard identification, decomposition of the customer function into sub-functions and effect chains, and in verification, such as testing functionalities in partial parameter spaces, managing the validation process, and determining the residual risk of the ADS in relation to scenarios.

Some new terms and definitions:

The **logical scenario class** is a logical scenario for which the descriptive parameters have been selected.

The **logical scenario instance** is a filled in logical scenario class. Each parameter has a range of values.

The **set of CORE scenarios** is defined as a set of logical scenarios that have certain properties: minimum set of logical scenarios, free of overlap with the underlying BASE scenarios, capable of representing ADS use cases and hazards, satisfying at least one system requirement, sufficiently complete representation of the ODD, ordered by essentiality.

Argument 1	We have developed a method with which we can describe (all) elements of the ODD sufficiently complete . By pointing to development steps exemplified by VVM. (Recommend that process XY is applied)
Argument 2	We have developed a formal proof with which we can show that we can generate a sufficiently complete model of the ODD
Argument 3	We have built a control step into our actual method that shows us that argument 2 is true within the validation, a validation step that shows that we do not find a new unknown scenario

Subthesis 1

A: The ODD Metamodel Approach provides a valid, sufficiently complete, relevant image of the ODD.

B: The consistent use of the ODD Metamodel Approach (OMA) throughout the development, verification and validation of an ADS ensures that the scenario-based VVM Methodology results in a defined and controlled risk to occupants and other road users within the ODD of the vehicle-integrated ADS.

Figure 5: Subthesis 1

In an inertial step, a set of functional and, based on them, a set of logical CORE scenarios are defined for a target ODD and a customer function. These scenarios are complemented by a scenario parameter database. Together they form the ODD metamodel or the ODD meta model approach (OMA). Based on the ODD metamodel, a systematic problem space analysis is performed. It provides an in-depth, fundamental understanding of the environment and risks the AD system must address.

A systematic hazard and risk analysis identifies both the events within the core scenarios in which a failure of the ego-vehicle function may occur, as well as systemically inherently hazardous conditions within the interaction between the ADS and its environment that must be avoided. ADS behavior and architecture are derived based on the ODD meta model approach (OMA).

The implementation is verified and validated in the next step. At the level of the components, the integrated system, and the integration into the vehicle, the ODD metamodel is used for scenario-based verification and validation. Scenario-based testing and statistical analysis of durability runs are based on the same scenario model that was used during the problem space analysis and specification of the target (safety) behavior of the ADS.

An additional validation step is the validation of the ODD metamodel. The ODD metamodel is used as a data filter or to transfer real-world observations into this model for coverage measurement or gap identification. Therefore, the ODD metamodel is validated in the real world to ensure that the ODD metamodel we use in design and V&V is a valid representation of the real-world target ODD with respect to the set of CORE scenarios and their declared parameters. This step reduces the epistemic uncertainty or "unknown knowns" in the ODD metamodel. The recursive approach within design and V&V reduces hazards or hazardous situations.

The safety argument being built within the VVM general methodology is based on the ability of the selected ADS architecture and vehicle integration to minimize the risk of behavioral insufficiency, detection, and component failures caused by ODD complexity.

The ODD Metamodel Approach (OMA) provides a valid, sufficiently complete, relevant image of the ODD. The use of OMA consistently ensures a representative problem/domain analysis, adequate ADS design and vehicle integration, and appropriate evidence from the extended scenario-based verification and validation process as described in the VVM general method.

2.2 Subthesis 2 – Mastering complexity by safety-by-design-approach

Safety by design is only possible on the basis of a coherent approach that combines design and verification and validation (V&V). This coherence is made possible by, among other things, a systematic integration of requirements and their V&V, digital traceability of work products including a data strategy. However, a systematic argumentation and explanation of the safety by design approach only succeeds if the essential argumentation steps correspond directly with the design and V&V artefacts and thus supports the safety argumentation. Thus, these theses and their argumentation address C3: "Safety argumentation and development process must correspond" and C6 "Continuous integration between verification and validation ecosystems must be enabled".

Argument 1	<p>The VVM development process structure corresponds to the perspectives of argumentation: The central argumentation principle is the application of different perspectives of system-behavior for the systematic analysis of risks/gaps. The Layers of the VVM process structure is set up in accordance to these perspectives: capability layer - required behavior, engineering layer - implemented behavior and real-world layer - real-world behavior. Thus, the evidences generated by the design and V&V domains effectively and efficiently support the argumentation of safety.</p>
Argument 2	<p>Semantic reproducibility of the central process artifacts enables chains of argumentation: Each central process artifact generated by the VVM developments framework represents the relevant requirements (qualities) of the preceding process artifact. This way the argumentation chain and the development flow are synchronized so that a continuous chain of reasoning (argumentation) regarding safety is made possible across the system hierarchies and avoids therefore an "explosion of argumentation-paths".</p>
Argument 3	<p>Consistent use of metrics enables transferability of requirements: The traceability and transferability of quantitative requirements of central process artifacts based on the consistent use of metrics and thus enables quantitative argumentation chains across the entire range of system hierarchies.</p>

Subthesis 2

The proposed VVM development process structures in a well-founded way a comprehensive safety-by-design approach whereby a systematic argumentation of safety is supported and complexity efficiently mastered.

Figure 6: Subthesis 2

2.3 Subthesis 3 – The Risk Management Core

Showing safety for a system in very different aspects while at the same time mastering increasing complexity requires a holistic approach, that is generic enough but is still precise for all of its applications. The Risk management Core forms this framework to address both challenge 1 “to develop a definition of safety and safe systems on the road” and challenge 3 “Safety argumentation and development process have to correspond” that are detailed in chapter 1.3 VVM goals, challenges and solution space. This is because the safety argumentation can directly follow the structure and the evidence resulting from the output of the Risk Management Core.

The Risk Management Core is designed along the solution space elements “Explainable fulfilment of Societal Safety Expectations” and “End-to-end Risk Management” that are explained in chapter 4.3.1.

Argument 1	The Risk Management Core is a systematic approach to assess and treat risks that are potentially introduced during operation of an ADS so that the threshold of an "absence of unreasonable risk" is satisfied . According to established industry standards, this is a necessary criterion to prove system safety.
Argument 2	This RMC has the benefit of being applicable in all lifecycle phases , e.g., during ADS operational design, target behavior definition, technical design, release and operation.
Argument 3	The RMC increases feasibility of assuring safety by reducing complexity by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • accounting for hazards and manages the risk from multiple safety perspectives such as Safety of the Intended Functionality (SoTIF), Functional Safety (FuSa) and others. • aggregating system risk of the same type or from the same scenario set. • combining Risk Acceptance Criteria from different sources and stakeholders, if they are of the same type.
Argument 4	The RMC includes a control loop that iteratively specifies and evaluates safety measures (including nominal risk reduction and integrity). In this turn the RMC aligns the estimated <i>actual system risk</i> with <i>accepted risk</i> <u>explicitly</u> . Thus, the RMC reduces the systems risk to an accepted level by applying <i>Risk Acceptance Criteria (RAC)</i> to determine the <i>accepted risk</i> , where the RACs are defined in line with societal expectations.
Argument 5	The RMC serves as common communication and explanation structure for different stakeholders for developers as well as authorities. Common understanding on safety and risk is a necessary criterion for the homologation of ADS equipped vehicles.

Subthesis 3

The Risk Management Core (RMC) provides a generic framework that allows both an ADS design based on societal safety expectations as well as providing evidence for the safety argumentation.

Figure 7: Subthesis 3

2.4 Subthesis 4 – The VVM Safety argumentation

ADS safety assurance presents a complex challenge and methods like the ones addressed by subtheses 1-3 are able to generate a multitude of development as well as verification and validation artifacts. Each of these artifacts plays a critical role in certifying the safety of ADS, yet their abundance, intricate detailing, and the complex interrelations among them pose a significant challenge. The primary issue is not solely the generation of these artifacts but weaving them into a coherent narrative that answers the fundamental question: "Why is this ADS safe enough?" This challenge underscores the necessity for a structured approach to safety argumentation, which not only organizes the available evidence into a comprehensive safety story but also ensures explainable compliance with normative requirements. The VVM safety argumentation structure, is designed to articulate an explicit ADS safety story, aligning seamlessly with the overarching goal of demonstrating and explaining how an ADS meets stringent safety benchmarks through a systematic, understandable, and stakeholder-inclusive process. In the following, six arguments are provided to substantiate subthesis 4.

Figure 8: Subthesis 4

Argument 1	The argumentation structure allows to address all important aspects to demonstrate the absence of unreasonable risks : functional safety, safety of the intended functionality, laws and regulation as well as ethics and safety performance.
Argument 2	The argumentation structure is tightly integrated with the three pillars of the VVM assurance framework : the risk management core, the VVM development process and the scenario-based assurance approach. Thus, the claim of the "absence of unreasonable risk" is systematically operationalized by balancing potential and actual risks with concrete safety measures to fulfill defined risk acceptance criteria.
Argument 3	The argumentation structure is built up respecting established argumentation principles . Therefore, it argues about claims regarding product performance, process performance, and confidence in product and process arguments. The approach for structuring the argument adds a dialectic perspective, which refutes potential counterarguments to the validity of the provided argument, systematically managing uncertainty with respect to this validity.

Argument 4	The product performance argumentation branch is decomposed along the VVM scenario-based assurance approach and considers the credibility of the technical V&V toolchain as a first-class argumentation need given the complexity of ADS V&V toolchains.
Argument 5	The process argumentation requires a justification for adequate process, method and tool definition with respect to problem space analysis, ADS design & development and verification & validation.
Argument 6	The provided GSN pattern for the VVM safety argumentation structure provides a starting point for safety argumentation teams to efficiently create safety cases in concrete ADS projects.

The proposed VVM development process structure enables a consistent separation of domain perspectives by combining **scenario-based testing**, **safety-by-design** and **risk management** with the perspective of **systematic reasoning** to develop and operate safety-related automotive systems. In this way, security becomes explainable and therefore **understandable for society** as well. The key to mastering this complexity is to consistently bring all aspects of the individual perspectives back together by maintaining clearly **defined interfaces** between them. This allows all aspects to be effectively integrated into **established automotive processes**.

3 VVM solution structure

The development of ADS is a complex task involving many stakeholders. PEGASUS supported the establishment of scenario-based testing across all test levels. VVM extended PEGASUS by including the development process, among other things. VVM proposes a framework integrating four perspectives to comprehensively develop a safe ADS.

Ensuring safe behavior within the operational design domain (ODD) is paramount. The framework emphasizes systematic integration of safety from the initial design stages to qualification. Three layers of system behavior guide the argumentation: the required capability, the specified engineering solution, and the real-world behavior of the integrated AD System. The framework’s goal is to ensure a solid foundation for arguing safe system behavior. It also explicitly distinguishes between autonomous driving (AD) design and the verification and validation (V&V) processes.

The VVM overall method comprises four interconnected processes areas or global “perspectives” to mitigate unreasonable risk. It connects scenario-based development and testing with overarching risk management, rendering the open-world context tangible. The systematic integration of safety into the development and testing process is a key aspect.

Enhanced transparency contributes to heightened societal acceptance of Automated Driving Systems (ADS), offering companies a decisive competitive advantage.

Figure 9: Four methodological processes to reach the goal : Assurance of a **safe** AD System by demonstrating the absence of **unreasonable risk**

PEGASUS, the predecessor project of VVM focused on testing. It established scenario-based testing in interconnected simulation in combination with proving ground tests and real driving to demonstrate a positive balance, respectively a reduced accident risk of an ADS in its ODD. PEGASUS also introduced a scenario database as an information basis. VVM extends this approach including the development process, with its dependencies like current standards (e.g. FUSA and SOTIF) towards a comprehensive view on the safety of ADS. At its core, VVM structures the complex requirements of the operational design area in a level of detail that a function can be developed adequately so that it can be operated safely in this domain. Additionally, VVM allows for argumentation of safety towards society. VVM proposes a framework that comprises of four perspectives:

The Global Development and V&V Perspective focusing on safety by design approach, enabling the process of design and V&V for argumentation and Dev-Ops ensuring the use of evidences from the design- and V&V-process within the argumentation.

The Scenario-based Development and Testing Perspective focusing on the process from development, especially the use of scenarios to ensure safe behavior, within design and V&V. It extends the established process by an approach to consistently use the same scenario meta model throughout the whole process.

The Risk Management Perspective focuses on a comprehensive and holistic concept of safety assessment and integration.

The Safety Argumentation Perspective focusing on a safety systematically argumentation how the safety of an ADS can be reasoned towards stakeholders of society.

3.1 Global Development and V&V perspective

The Global Development and V&V perspective focuses on the conceptual blocks present in the development process of an ADS and links these to the three layers, according to the views for safety argumentation, see Figure 10.

The argumentation of safety can essentially only be based on evidence of the development processes. Since the main idea of reasoning is to argue through different perspectives of behavior [required, specified and real] and the goal of reasoning is to systematically reduce gaps between these perspectives, these perspectives of behavior must be taken into account fundamentally in the development process. This is determined by three layers corresponding to the perspectives of the behavior. The horizontal layers (of behavioral perspectives) represent development and operating modes for the vertical domains design and verification and validation (V&V).

Figure 10: Global Development and V&V method

- The Capability Layer focuses on the composition of abstract requirements. Relevant claims e.g. societal, laws, standards or intended functions are transferred into ADS behavior according to its ODD and into related capabilities, including capabilities necessary for V&V.
- The Engineering Layer focuses on the system specification, structuring the decomposition of abstract requirements for the design specification of the ADS and the tests to validate and verify the ADS.
- The Real-World Layer focuses on the interaction of the final implementation with the real world, thus enabling the validation of the ADS behavior within an uncontrolled environment.

These three horizontal layers and the vertical domains [as design and V&V] provide an efficient and traceable decomposition of design and V&V enabling a coherent "safety-by design" approach according to the V-Model. Thus, each horizontal layer provides specific evidence of behavior, needed to argue behavioral safety of the system. The decomposition of design and V&V is also led by the risk-model and the ODD-meta-model and its scenario decomposition. Thus, Design and V&V are structured to support reasoning of system safety expressed by a purposefully argumentation and fulfilling the challenge 3: "Safety argumentation and development process must correspond" as also challenge 6: "Continuous integration between verification and validation ecosystems must be enabled".

3.2 Scenario-based Development and Testing perspective

Complementing the conceptual view, the Scenario-based Development and Testing perspective (Figure 11) focuses on the approach, how scenario-based methods can be applied to complement the development, confirmation and assurance process of a safe ADS. VVM proposes to extend the development process towards an early alignment of artifacts and safety requirements derived from

safety arguments, and an alignment of the formulation of the requirements to be used as evidence through the validation and verification process later.

Figure 11: Scenario-Based Testing and Development method

Having safety argumentation in mind, the ODD meta model comprising of a set of core scenarios is introduced as a new tool that can be used in the design as well as the V&V process.

In the design process: The introduction of the ODD meta model allows to perform problem space analysis, System Design, and Safeguarding of the System on the same set of scenarios representing the ODD. The problem space analysis provides a deep understanding of the problem space: It can serve as the basis for the hazard and risk analysis, the definition of safety goals as well as for the integration of stakeholder needs (e.g. legal, society or ethical) in the system behavior and design. Furthermore, the Risk Management Core which defines a process framework for managing risk especially in the context of specifying system behavior and handling hazardous events serves to consistently use of controlled and managed risk throughout design and safeguarding.

During Validation and Verification: Using the ODD meta model allows for V&V on the same ODD meta model from Hazard and Risk Analysis as well as System Design. This results in the new V&V task of validating the sufficient validity of the current set of CORE scenarios. In this task evidence must be provided that validates that the CORE scenario and associated properties provide adequate coverage of the real scenarios from the target domain. The evaluation of measures resulting from risk managed system behavior is added, which it is essential to prove that the system behaves at least in such a way that the risk acceptance criteria are met in its ODD. And the V&V concept gets a focus on an assurance related organization of V&V: test objectives, test levels, test platforms and test strategies are linked by the V&V concept and aligned with the need for artifacts and evidence of building the safety assurance argument.

Introducing the meta-model ODD, the requirements of the system are pre-structured enabling an intelligent integration of simulation strategies, proving grounds and on-road tests as well as a holistic,

feasible validation, which starts early in the development and is an integral part of the development process.

3.3 Risk Management Perspective

The Risk Management perspective Figure 12 is introduced as part of the VVM framework as it can serve as basis for multiple purposes. The Risk Management perspective collects all hazards and safety goals of the ADS allowing creation of safe target behavior definition, the alignment of system risks with acceptance criteria, the risk estimation of specific system elements as well as the risk evaluation at start of production.

The multitude of necessary safety considerations, whether it is safety of the intended function, functional safety and other needs to be managed. For this purpose, the Risk Management Core (RMC) perspective is proposed within the VVM framework. The RMC represents the continuous processing of actual risks to align with acceptable risks. It establishes risk as the leading measure for safety, aggregates all system risk aspects and aligns the system risk with risk acceptance criteria.

Figure 12: The Risk Management Core method

The Risk Management Core supports both challenge 1 “to develop a definition of safety and safe systems on the road” and challenge 3 “Safety argumentation and development process have to correspond”. This is because the safety argumentation can directly follow the structure and the evidence resulting from the output of the Risk Management Core. The Risk Management Core is designed along the solution space elements “Explainable fulfilment of Societal Safety Expectations” and “End-to-end Risk Management”.

3.4 Safety Argumentation Perspective

The Safety Argumentation perspective is introduced within the VVM framework to reason why an ADS is safe, i.e. why unreasonable risks are absent during operation. This perspective is proposed to hold all sources of ADS risks and structure the way Figure 13 to decompose the top safety claim

“absence of unreasonable risk” into manageable sub claims. Evidence from all perspectives of the VVM assurance framework is used in the safety argumentation process, see Figure 13.

The Risk Management Core is used as a reference model to reason alignment of estimated risk with accepted risk, the Scenario-based Development and Testing approach serves as a reference model to reason that the ADS development and V&V provides confidence. Global Development and V&V serves to reason that the specification of required capabilities, their engineering and validation in controlled and uncontrolled real-world conditions are completed.

The VVM Safety Argumentation perspective structures the argumentation needs for ADS risk prediction based on assumptions about relevant development and V&V artifacts. It serves as a starting point for argument development in concrete ADS projects considering company-specific assurance methods and V&V.

layers in-line with the relevant standards, corresponding to existing or future tooling and must be systematically integrated into the fleet operation entities.

The feasibility of argumentation is enabled by:

- Consequent assignment of responsibilities to domains (Meta Layers of AS) and their seamless interaction,
- Reproducibility of the elements of the Assurance Framework with respect to argumentation. Within a chain, each representation of elements unites the requirements of the previous representations, thus avoiding explosion of “argumentation paths”,
- Consistency of metrics: Use of metrics which can transfer between representations and enable traceability,
- Correspondence of Meta Layers of Assurance Framework.

Figure 13: The VVM Safety Argumentation structure method

3.5 Enabler, Premises and Summary of Solution

Consistent use of metrics

The traceability and transferability of quantitative requirements of central process artifacts is based on the consistent use of metrics and thus enables quantitative argumentation chains across the entire range of system hierarchies. One of the biggest outcomes of the VVM-method consists of the separation and of the linking of the four perspectives - mentioned above. Thus, the complete system of links between the perspectives as also the decomposition of process artifacts at each layer of these perspectives should be based on a consistent use of metrics. Only in this way will the power of the overall VVM methodology be unfolded.

Adaptivity to ODD changes

VV Methods has made significant steps towards safeguarding Automated Driving Systems when presented with a given ODD. In the long run, we must expect the given ODD to change. For example, traffic rules are adapted, and new types of traffic participants arise. Therefore, the system must be updated. A full re-run of all safeguarding procedures at every update would lead to economic infeasibility of the product. An important step towards applicability is therefore updating safety cases such that only evidence for the relevant parts is re-generated, which eventually establishes economic feasibility. This implies a complete and harmonized formally described ODD on its several layers in-line with the relevant standards, corresponding to existing or future tooling and must be systematically integrated into the fleet operation entities.

Summary

All four perspectives of the VVM overall framework bring together the most important aspects to ensure that an ADS does not pose any unreasonable risk. Thus, VVM contributes to increasing the transparency and acceptance of the safety ensuring process through this comprehensive method. The application of safety argumentation requires consistent alignment of scenario-based development and testing comprehensive risk management and argumentation as well as an explicit definition of their linking interfaces in order to make the open-world context tangible. This approach directly strengthens competitiveness, as companies can gain a decisive advantage by systematically integrating safety into the development and testing process.

- ▶ The assurance argumentation enables consistent and traceable decomposition from claims down to verification & validation, thus explainable compliance for release of vehicles to road is enabled.
- ▶ Design and V&V must support the argumentation with evidence. Thus, a seamless interaction between Argumentation and Design and V&V, ideally compliant to relevant industry standards is necessary. An enabling solution for this challenge is given by the assurance framework.

Finally, VVM has developed a methodology as common basis to develop future Automated Driving Systems (ADS) integrating societally accepted risk management. The VVM framework integrates all perspectives needed to develop a safe ADS integrating simulation strategies with proving grounds and on-road tests, enabling feasible validation and verification (V&V) procedures into comprehensive, structured, integrable in established industrial processes.

4 Detailed Description of developed sub-methods within the four described perspectives

4.1 The Global Development & Operation Perspective

4.1.1 Main Concept for Safety Assurance

is proposed by the proof of safe behavior within the ODD by an argumentation. The main systematic is to extend “behavioral safe ODD areas” via extrapolation (figure1-left), referring to V&V-evidences (Figure 14: Main idea: assurance of save behavior at ODD-right).

Figure 14: Main idea: assurance of save behavior at ODD

The Argumentation of Assurance is considered as a main enabler for a traceable decomposition of societal claims and thus for explainable compliance in order to e.g. release vehicles to road.

The main idea of the argumentation is to argue by different perspectives of behavior [required, specified and real]. Goal is to systematically achieve gaps between these perspectives (Figure 15: association of argumentation concept and layers of development framework-left). If the argumentation can only rely on evidences of the development process, the perspectives of behavior should be represented within the framework of development. This is established by three layers, corresponding to the perspectives (Figure 15: association of argumentation concept and layers of development framework). The horizontal layers constitute modes of development and operation defining the vertical domains Design and Verification and Validation.

Argumentation Concept

Framework

Figure 15: association of argumentation concept and layers of development framework²

- **Capability Layer: Composition of abstract requirements** Relevant societal claims as laws/standards & market proposition are transferred into the “required behavior” and related capabilities including V&V capabilities.
- **Engineering Layer: System specification by decomposition of the abstract requirements** leads to the specification of the behavior by the Design and its proof by Verification within a controlled environment.
- **Real World Layer: Interaction of the physical system with the uncontrolled environment** enables Validation of behavior with focus on resilience in open context over the complete life cycle.

4.1.2 Interaction of Development and Argumentation

- ▶ The goals of development, e.g. release of vehicles and other goals should correspond to the claims of argumentation. The strategy of argumentation relies on the concepts of Design and V&V and the risk modeling, vice versa - the argumentation provides rules to shape precise and suitable evidences, see Figure 16.

² **Reference to Figure 15** : J. E. Stellet, T. Brade, A. Poddey, S. Jesenski and W. Branz, "Formalisation and algorithmic approach to the automated driving validation problem," 2019 IEEE Intelligent - with minor changes

Figure 16: association of development structure to argumentation structure

Why establish a Capability Layer?

- ▶ **Complexity can be mastered by abstraction.** Capabilities can be argued to cover safe behavior, including safety concerns, thus the decomposition of system requirements derived out of capabilities could be used for a consistent and traceable verification and validation.
- ▶ **Traceable Decomposition by Argumentation**
The safety argumentation on abstract level of behavior enables one to argue a claim referring to safety acceptance criteria e.g. a Positive Risk Balance as a main reference based on accident statistics.

Summary

- ▶ The assurance argumentation enables consistent and traceable decomposition from claims down to verification & validation, thus explainable compliance for release of vehicles to road is enabled.
- ▶ Design and V&V must support the argumentation with evidences. Thus, a seamless interaction between Argumentation and Design and V&V, ideally compliant to relevant industry standards is necessary. An enabling solution for this challenge is given by the assurance framework.

4.1.3 Safety expectation and fulfillment

- ▶ For increasing automation, the focus of safety moves to overall behavior.
- ▶ Safety is defined by absence of unreasonable risk (automotive consensus), see Figure 17.
- ▶ ADS products are safe because they meet societal safety expectations, thus societal stakeholders define risk acceptance criteria.

Figure 17: Relation of hazards, risk, safety measures and criteria

Conclusion #1: The interrelation between risk acceptance criteria, risk from hazardous events and safety measures must be modeled ► **Solution: Assurance Framework – Risk Management** (Figure 18: Assurance Framework – all four Meta Layers right above)

Approach to extrapolate “safe behavior areas”

- Select the risk-sensitive areas of behavior by decomposition of ODD and design along risk model.
- Build extrapolation models for safe behavior and define risk and performance thresholds along with risk model.

Conclusion #2: Design and V&V and the ODD must be decomposed along risk model according to behavior and related capabilities ► **Solution: Assurance Framework - Development and Operation Global / Scenarios** (Figure 18: Assurance Framework – all four Meta Layers left)

Compliance must be explained to society

Approach: Argumentation of safe behavior over ODD.

Conclusion #3: Top-Down structure of argumentation, following its rules, based on concepts from development and operation and risk management ► **Solution: Assurance Framework - Argumentation** (Figure 18: Assurance Framework – all four Meta Layers right down)

4.1.3.1 Feasibility of Argumentation

- **Consequent assignment of responsibilities** to domains (Meta Layers of AS) and their seamless interaction.
- **Reproducibility of the Elements** of the Assurance Framework with respect to argumentation. Within a chain, each representation of elements unites the requirements of the previous representations, thus avoiding explosion of “argumentation paths”.
- **Consistency of metrics** Use of metrics which can transfer between representations ► enable traceability.

► **Correspondence of Meta Layers of Assurance Framework – examples:**

- **Global:** Target behaviour / ODD ⇔ **Scenarios:** Functional / Logical Core Scenarios
- **Global:** Acceptance Criteria / Top Goals ⇔ **Risk Management:** Risk Acceptance Criteria

Figure 18: Assurance Framework – all four Meta Layers

4.1.4 Global Development: V&V Perspective

4.1.4.1 Path of Verification and Validation

The goal of V&V is to contribute to a holistic statement on safety by providing evaluated test results. As an integral part of the assurance framework, it is dependent on input concerning safety capabilities, requirements regarding the V&V concept and information on the system design.

Adapted to the 2-step approach in the development of functional (solution independent) and technical (technological solution) design, the handling of the tests is also divided into a functional and a technical step.

Furthermore, logical scenario instances are required input from the respective process into the test planning.

Approach of V&V Concept

Test cases for verification and validation (V&V) are generated from the decomposition of system, ODD, and TOP Goals requirements to achieve safety.

The sum of the test cases from V&V at all system levels provides the evidence to argue that the system actual behavior represents the target behavior in the defined ODD and thus meets the TOP Goals e.g. “safety by absence of unreasonable risk”.

Procedure

1. Define risk thresholds along a risk model and decompose ODD and design down to performance thresholds.
2. Verification until performance thresholds are proven otherwise iterate development.
3. Validation to prove that risk is below thresholds otherwise iterate development.

The more verification, the less effort for validation.

Aggregation / Evaluation concept

Aggregation of V&V-evidences follows the argumentation, thus the decomposition of the system and its risk-modeling. Hereby evidences as test results, methods evaluation and scenario exposure are involved. The composition of the argumentation is done by bottom-up aggregation of evidences. Thus, aggregation follows the break-down of argumentation from bottom up. The result is the composition of the argumentation, see (Figure 19).

Figure 19: The aggregation of evidences follows the argumentation , thus the composition of the argumentation is done bottom up

V&V application for behavior based on framework

The “V&V-path” follows the perspectives of argumentation and thus the layers of the assurance framework (Figure 20: The path validation and verification mapped on the Global development & operation perspective.). Targeted behavior and required behavior at the Capability Layer are derived from specified and monitored behavior on the Engineering Layer which is derived from real behavior at the Real-World Layer.

Figure 20: The path validation and verification mapped on the Global development & operation perspective.

The V&V concept must meet a wide variety of criteria, such as sufficient test coverage with the required feasibility and the highest possible efficiency, to provide appropriate evidence in line with the argumentation. To do this, it is necessary to cleverly combine different methods. The figure (Figure 21: Verification and Validation concerning coverage of design and ODD) below illustrates the approach of combining verification and validation to address the contradictory challenges.

Figure 21: Verification and Validation concerning coverage of design and ODD

When it comes to test coverage, the first question that arises is reference. In a simplified view, the test space is spanned by two variables, the product design and the operating environment (ODD) in which the product must prove itself. Ideally, both should be 100% covered. While the design should be firmly and completely known by the time it is released, the ODD can also have unknown features and may also be subject to changes over time that cannot be predicted. Everything that is known can theoretically be tested in a targeted manner.

This is where verification comes in. A decomposition of design and ODD allows targeted and structured testing at different system levels and under a wide variety of conditions. The fact that there

are limits to this is due to the large number of parameters used to describe the influences from the operating environment, the complex architecture of the product and the almost endless combinatorics of both. To deal with this efficiently, the decomposed parts of the product and environment can be evaluated to what extent they play a role in safety. Aspects such as the probability of scenarios as well as the potential consequences or the controllability of situations come into play. In this way, with the naturally limited number of tests, you can focus on the sensitive areas first. Consequently, fewer safety-critical events are to be expected in the remaining test room. Nevertheless, an unspecified residual risk remains.

At this point validation comes into play, which has several objectives at once. First, it allows the identification of unknown critical events. Their analysis and evaluation of their causes opens the possibility of expanding the testing space of verification where this seems sensible. This reduces the unknown area in the given test room. It is much easier not to have to capture all unknown scenarios, but to focus only on those with critical events. Second, critical events can also occur in the validation that are known but have not been classified as relevant as part of the verification. The verification can also be supplemented with these cases in the future, if necessary. Thirdly, validation makes it possible to assess the residual risk remaining outside of verification as described above. For this purpose, suitable metrics can also be used to record criticalities that are far before the actual accident. The advantage is that they can be observed on a correspondingly much larger scale, as they do not lead to damage in most cases due to reserves and the compensatory capacity of the transport system in total. Statistical methods can be used to quantitatively describe the residual risk based on the probability of occurrence of such critical events and the significance level (confidence range), which depends on the number of kilometers driven.

In summary, verification is necessary, validation sufficient. However, it is only the targeted verification concentrated on safety-sensitive areas, the continuous reduction of potentially critical events in both unknown and known situations, the use of special metrics for the detection of critical situations in the more frequently observed early phases leading to a potential accident, combined with the possibility of cost-reduced and cost-effective expansion of the road tests through silent testing (before and after SOP) to ensure not only the feasibility of the statistical assessment of the residual risk, but also achieve maximum efficiency.

Interaction to Argumentation

An assurance argumentation requires two main aspects of the V&V domain:

- Concepts on which the argumentation is enabled to build up a strategy.
- Suitable evidences.

Both inputs must follow the rules / systematic of the argumentation.

Interaction to Risk Management

Risk management requires evidences for the assessment of specified risk mitigation of the measures of the safety concepts. The aspects of evidences must follow the requirements of the defined risk modeling and especially the acceptance criteria. This supports the propagation of risk modeling to the technical system.

ODD Coverage and Validation KPI's

Verifying the coverage of the ODD through the mileage of the field tests performed so far goes hand in hand with validating the completeness of the metamodel for the ODD. The goal is to demonstrate the coverage of the defined meta model for the ODD in all its relevant dimensions, while identifying any undiscovered / missing scenario classes or relevant domain characteristics. In both cases, the scenario database, as a component of the ODD metamodel, could be used to scan and evaluate real-world data. When collecting the data, it is necessary to consider the observation problem by using appropriate ground truth sensor technology and algorithms. Relevant test criteria are an appropriate percentage of coverage of CORE scenarios and parameter classes. The intermediate evaluation of the achieved OOD coverage is used to guide further test operations. Test end criteria of is: Field-based testing has covered a relevant* subset of the scenario classes in the metamodel for the ODD and identified during the domain analysis within the system specification with the detection of 0 critical defects.

(* Relevant due to the controllability problem of field-based testing, where a set of concrete scenarios specified in the ODD model may be extremely rare or difficult and dangerous to reproduce in real traffic on public roads).

Scenario-based Evaluating of residual risk

For the evaluation of the residual risk, the same risk acceptance criteria and the same risk evaluation function are used as in the Risk Management Core.

For this objective, an evaluation function is used that determines the collision risk of the release of the ADS in the CORE scenarios for the severity classes S0, S1, S2, S3. The derived safety goal is then, for example, to identify collision-relevant parameter sets / boundaries or areas in the parameter space to be tested. The evaluation of the residual risk of the ADS in the scenario-based metamodel of the ODD is used for an abstract representation of the scenario environment. This implies that the residual risk for each CORE scenario must be evaluated in its parameter space. Core scenarios are decomposable into a scenario, a description layer of the scenario, and parameters declared in the layer. The evaluation of residual risk is therefore performed for each CORE scenario individually and successively. The parameter space of the CORE scenario instance is searched using an intelligent search-based algorithm to determine the probability that an S0 to S3 collision will occur. This type of simulation-based testing is used to prove functional correctness and compliance with risk acceptance criteria while the system is operating with the implemented behavior. It verifies the ability of the decomposed data fusion, planning, and acting algorithms to handle the range of (known) concrete traffic scenarios correctly with acceptable risk.

KPIs from measurements are evaluated and used to validate the simulation model to estimate the real performance of the sensor cluster. In this way, it is possible to identify corner cases that can be addressed in advance of the model validation by means of a test on the proving ground.

Test end criteria

The test end criteria consist of different elements. The risk acceptance criteria, among other things, compliance with the regulations, the behavioral law, the ethical and methodological standards of testing belong to it.

4.1.4.2 Requirements Decomposition to Design Constraints

VVM shows in [1] how to systematically derive **Top Goals** for automated driving from concerns of legislation, authorities, market actors, society or ethics. These needs are formally analyzed on behavioral level [2] and formulated as scenario-specific **Behavioral Requirements**.

Besides further stakeholder needs, Behavioral Requirements are the main input when composing **System Requirements** [3].

As described in [3], a useful **Functional Architecture** is developed to satisfy the System Requirements by means of functions, their hierarchy, sequences, and interfaces.

Logical **Architecture** groups functions and covers non-functional requirements using technical concepts and principles. Having a Logical Architecture mitigates the impact of requirements and technology changes on system design [4]. The requirements for logical elements and interfaces are derived from system requirements.

The resulting **Technical Design** implements logical elements and their interfaces by specific technology. The requirements for technical elements and interfaces are derived from requirements for logical elements and interfaces.

[4] claims: "Once the top-level set of system requirements has been established, it is necessary to allocate and flow them down to successively lower levels. As the allocation and flow-down process is repeated, it is essential that **traceability** be maintained to ensure that all system-level requirements are satisfied in the resulting design."

As figure A shows with blue arrows, requirements, architectural elements, and their interfaces are interconnected and related to each other:

- Horizontally on the same level of abstraction
- Vertically across the levels of abstraction

This bidirectional traceability is quite hard to maintain manually, e.g. by manually assigning them unique IDs. Tools for requirements management or model-based systems engineering should be used instead.

More than the technical aspects of traceability, the qualitative aspects are challenging at the transition between Capability Layer and Engineering Layer:

- The quality measures of Behavioral Requirements are of type risk: Risk reduction needs and their respective integrity impose **Design Constraints**.
- The quality measures of Functional Requirements use technical values, e.g., physical values like distances. These technical values in turn have impacts on the target behavior.

The alignment between quality measures of Behavioral Requirements and quality measures of Functional Requirements is achieved by evaluating resulting system performance, following a scenario-based approach. For safety considerations, such an evaluation provides the basis for the estimation of residual risks.

Requirements arising from further safety considerations like Safety of the Intended Functionality (SOTIF) or Cyber Security are handled analogously: We argue that the Automated Driving System

does not pose unreasonable risk in its Operational Design Domain, if it satisfies the Behavioral Safety Requirements. **Concerns** are explicitly integrated in the underlying behavior specification process.

Figure 22: Requirements flow through the system design

References:

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- [2] N. F. Salem et al., “Ein Beitrag zur durchgängigen, formalen Verhaltensspezifikation automatisierter Straßenfahrzeuge.” arXiv, Sep. 15, 2022. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2209.07204. (English publication upcoming)
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- [4] Walden, D. D., Roedler, G. J., Forsberg, K., Hamelin, R. D. & Shortell, T. M. (eds.) (2015). Systems Engineering Handbook: A Guide for System Life Cycle Processes and Activities. Hoboken, NJ: Wiley.

4.1.4.3 Flow of requirements and architecture

Target behavior is specified in system requirements which consist of functional [safety] requirements and behavioral [safety] requirements, whereas behavioral safety requirement. The target behavior is specified in system requirements, which consist of functional [safety] requirements and behavioral [safety] requirements. Behavioral safety requirements specify solution-independent safety-related behavior or solution-independent safety measures, including safety-related attributes that specify the level of risk reduction required and integrity. In functional design, the behavioral safety requirements have been translated into a unique set of functional safety requirements, which may consist of performance requirements that use technical values to define system performance. The alignment between quality measures of behavioral safety requirements and performance requirements is achieved by evaluating system performance, following a scenario-based approach. Back at the behavioral level, such an evaluation provides the basis for estimating residual risks. The set of (system) performance requirements are test criteria in test cases in the verification when specifying and adding pass/fail criteria. Traceability is provided by a requirements management system. The system requirements are used to define the functional architecture. The goal is to compose the functionalities in such a way that architecture, i.e., the hierarchical construction of functionalities, can be decomposed to its lowest level. During the specification of the functional architecture, the system requirements are also refined.

4.1.4.4 Requirements for Test Execution

As shown in the previous chapter, requirements are derived from target behavior and decomposed across the design artifacts. Besides design, these requirements are also necessary for verification purposes:

- **Functional Test Specifications** are one output of the **Test Planning** process. They utilize elements of the **Functional Architecture & Design** (including related requirements) as test objects, see upper magnifying glass in Figure 23.

Figure 23: Test Objects for Functional and Technical Test Specifications

- **Technical Test Specifications** are one output of the **Test Orchestration** process. They utilize elements of the **Technical Architecture & Design** (including requirements) as test objects, see lower magnifying glass in Figure 23.
- Tests are conducted according to the Technical Test Specifications in the **Test Execution** process. They utilize elements of the **Physical Construction** (implementing the technical design and its requirements) as test object.

Figure 24 marks the relation of the mentioned design and test processes in the Global Development and V&V Perspective of the VVM Assurance Framework.

Figure 24: Relation of the design and test processes in the VVM Argumentation Framework

Process flow within V&V (Figure 25)

V&V Concept - Systematize the acquisition of the evidence required for the safety case with the goal of demonstrating compliance with a safe target behavior for an ADS.

Test Planning – Define the functional test space and provide functional test specifications.

Test Orchestration – Derive technical test specifications from functional test specifications, using knowledge about technical design and test platforms. Distribute test cases to test instances.

Test Execution – Conduct tests following the technical test specifications.

Tech. Evaluation – Technical evaluation of test data generated from the execution of tests, corresponding to the test orchestration.

Func. Evaluation – Assess functions based on the input from tech. evaluation, corresponding to the test planning. Aggregate results to provide evidence for the safety of the ADS.

Figure 25: Structure of V&V within the Assurance Framework

4.1.4.5 Handling of Concerns within V&V

Concerns are indications of a subjective (e.g., assessments) or objective (e.g., measurement results) or normative (e.g., standards & laws) nature, which must be given special consideration regarding the scope of the test. Concerns must be addressed to the appropriate level. For example, functional concerns refer to functional design, while scenario concerns refer to scenarios that need to be considered. According to their level, such concerns are received at the appropriate point to weigh their relevance for safety in the context, e.g., of the functional design or the logical scenario instances.

4.2 The Scenario-based Development and Testing Perspective

4.2.1 Aside: The role of "reality abstraction" in the scenario-based development of an ADS

Scenarios represent a central component of the VVM test and the design concept. As part of the overall VVM method, scenarios are consistently employed as a model for the development space, as well as the validation and test space. Through the continuous validation of the scenario model, this contributes to the closing of the specification gap.

The term "**reality abstraction**" refers to a method of creating a sufficiently complete scenario-based model of the ODD. The result is a set of CORE scenarios (functional or logical) and a scenario (parameter) database. These enable the formalization or modeling of the ODD (here: traffic and environmental conditions in the target ODD of the customer function). The result of the reality abstraction, which is the three-element set of CORE scenarios (functional and logical) and scenario (parameter) database, is referred to as the ODD metamodel. (See Figure 26)

Figure 26: ODD meta model defined through reality abstraction

The starting point is the six-level model that was developed in PEGASUS for the highway use case. The application of the model to an urban ODD requires adaptations in levels 1 and 4. A novel concept was developed to describe the fundamental constellations or basic scenarios for the dynamic objects of level 4, which can be utilized in both the highway application area—roads with multi-lane and separated directional lanes—and in urban domains. This approach is further complemented by a concept of holistic urban driving scenarios that are categorized according to the degree of interaction with other instances. The novel scenario types combine the structural elements of level 1 with the interaction patterns of level 4. The concept will be presented in greater detail later in this chapter (see #Holistic urban driving scenario concept). It should be noted that the term "scenario" has different meanings and forms of representation throughout the development process, as different development phases have varying requirements for the use of scenarios due to the completion of different development steps. The concept phase describes scenarios at a high level of abstraction. System development and the test specification in the context of validation and verification require a description of the scenarios in parameter ranges of the physical state space to structure testing in test planning. The actual testing, i.e., the execution and evaluation of a test case, requires clearly defined scenarios to be tested. To meet this requirement, scenarios are defined on three levels of abstraction: functional, logical and concrete.

Functional scenario: A functional scenario is a behavior-based description of a scenario on a semantic level. It delineates the entities and their relationships with each other in a manner that is free of contradictions. The description can be verbal (in natural language or with a formal language), visual (graphical), or in another way.

A functional scenario describes the relevant actors and their basic maneuvers under consideration. A functional scenario is a deliberately unspecific description of a scenario in natural language that leaves open not only concrete parameters or their spectra, but also some basic information. (Definition from PEGASUS)

A **logical scenario** is a formalized description of a scenario. It has declared attributes and parameters for the corresponding functional scenario. It uses the description system of the 6-level model. A logical scenario may contain unrestricted parameter spaces, restricted parameter ranges, or, in the case of discrete parameters, their enumerations and the dependencies of parameters.

A logical scenario formally describes relevant actors and their considered basic maneuvers. Entities and relationships among them are formulated parametrically. Ranges for the parameters and relationships between parameter ranges can be specified. (Definition from PEGASUS)

A logical scenario may exhibit two special characteristics:

4. All parameters are defined, and they have not yet been assigned a parameter range.
5. All parameters are defined, and each has been assigned a parameter range.

To express this linguistically, new terms have been introduced:

The **logical scenario class** is a logical scenario for which the descriptive parameters have been defined.

A **logical scenario instance** is a scenario class in which each parameter has been assigned a value range that is both valid and applicable.

A **concrete scenario** is created by instantiating a logical scenario instance by filling it with concrete values.

A concrete scenario assigns concrete values to all parameters of a logical scenario. It models a discrete assignment/selection of parameters via possibly continuous spectra of a logical scenario.

A concrete scenario is a parameterized model with fixed parameters for the chronological sequence of scenes (logical scenario), which begins with a concrete start scene. All parameters that describe a traffic event are explicitly defined in the concrete scenario. Exactly one concrete scenario is instantiated at any one time. (Definition from PEGASUS)

The levels of abstraction, particularly the functional, logical, and concrete levels, are adapted to the different requirements of test steps in the development process. They enable developers to use an ODD model consistently and to integrate the progressive gain in knowledge in the same model. The verbal or graphical description forms serve this purpose. The tools used in the process are another addressee. Formal languages, in particular the OpenSCENARIO and OpenDRIVE languages proposed in PEGASUS, are employed here to facilitate a link between the simulation and its development and test platforms.

To utilize ontologies, such as the AUTO ontology, a specialized type of formalized description is essential. This leads to the definition of an abstract scenario. An abstract scenario is a formalized, declarative description of a scenario with the focus on representing complex relationships, in particular cause-effect relationships. The semantics of the description are based on the verbalized ontology. An abstract scenario is machine-readable and generates a scenario description language

such as OpenSCENARIO and OPENDRIVE (see Settings from PEGASUS). Abstraction levels define the level of detail in the description of a scenario. However, the "grammar" and "vocabulary" used to describe the entities, their relationships, and the basic behavior of a scenario are also important in the application of these constructs. VVM uses the systematic 6-level model established with PEGASUS (see Figure 27). The model was extended for use on highways and urban areas.

Figure 27: 6-level model established within PEGASUS

4.2.2 Holistic urban driving scenario concept

The 6-level model structures the traffic events into six levels, which can be seen in Figure 28.

Figure 28: 6-level structuring of traffic

According to this structure, there are three description areas for the scenario concept: the description of the road and surroundings (levels 1-3), the dynamic objects and their relationships (level 4) and the environmental influences and digital information (levels 5 and 6). In the first step of the scenario concept, the perspective of a road user (the ego) is selected, and the traffic events are described

from his perspective in sections of the traffic space (e.g., intersection, road, traffic circle, highway section, highway ramp), which is referred to as an enveloping scenario.

A particular challenge in the derivation of scenarios is the description of the dynamics and interactions of road users. To reduce complexity, the various aspects of traffic dynamics are described individually using so-called concepts. Examples are the crossing maneuver of the ego-vehicle and the type of crossing conflict between two road users. These concepts can be divided into three categories:

Individual concepts only affect the ego vehicle.

Bilateral concepts concern the interaction between the ego vehicle and exactly one road user.

Global concepts relate to the type of transport and environment

By combining these concepts, base scenarios can be systematically defined. The advantage of this approach is that it reduces the complexity of the traffic situation by utilizing combinatorics. This simplifies scenario identification, generation and payout in the simulation. The concepts, their types and possible combinations are recorded in an ontology. This helps to link an argumentation with the scenario concept and other components of the methodology. The combinatorics are also carried out and explicitly documented. The set of basic scenarios generated in this way comprises fewer than 300 scenarios.

The basic scenarios can be understood as building blocks from which longer and more complex traffic events are put together (see diagram above). Such combinations are referred to as combined scenarios. When combined, basic scenarios can run both sequentially and in parallel. For more details see VVM deliverable D12.

4.2.3 From data to logical scenarios with parameter distributions

The intermediate goal of the VVM methodology is to define logical scenario instances that can be systematically tested. For this purpose, parameters must be defined for the scenarios of the scenario concept. The property of the basic scenarios that are combined from concepts is used for this purpose. Accordingly, parameters can be defined separately for each concept. Combining the parameters of the concepts results in the parameters of the basic scenarios, analogous to the definition of the scenarios themselves. In addition to parameters that are used for payout in the simulation, for example, attributes can be determined using a similar procedure that only fulfills a descriptive task but are not necessarily transferable to the payout. These are particularly relevant when identifying scenarios in traffic data and strengthening the filtering options in the search for specific scenarios. Parameters and attributes can be derived from criticality analysis, for example. This allows a set of logical scenarios to be generated.

To obtain logical scenario instances, the distribution of the parameters is required. To enable an estimation of the risk in later steps of the methodology, these distributions should correspond to the real occurrence of the parameter in the ODD. For this purpose, actual traffic must be analyzed. To do this, trajectories of traffic scenarios are identified in measurement data using algorithms and the associated parameters and attributes are determined. This is where the composition of basic scenarios from concepts pays off again, as it significantly reduces the amount of logic required. If a set of scenarios and their parameters is identified in this way, the underlying distribution and the relationships between the parameters can be approximated. Hybrid graphs, for example, are suitable

for this purpose. Logical scenario instances can thus be determined. For more details see VVM deliverable D12.

4.2.4 Database with logical urban traffic scenarios

As mentioned in the previous section, the approximated distributions should correspond to the real occurrence of the scenarios in the ODD. In addition to scenarios from knowledge sources, this requires a large and extensive amount of traffic data and automated processing of this data. A scenario database can be used to process and manage the resulting scenarios. This takes care of managing the input data, identifying the scenarios and their parameters and attributes. The database, as sketched in Figure 29, generates logical scenario instances from the concrete scenarios stored in the database and provides analysis tools for the user. Furthermore, the scenario database offers options for filtering the scenarios according to characteristics or categories relevant to the user's use case and provides simulation scenarios derived from the scenarios in the form of OpenSCENARIO XML.

Figure 29: Structuring of the scenario database

An interface is required to automatically process data from different sources. The OMEGA format was defined in VVM for this purpose, see Figure 30. It is a hierarchical data format that includes information from all 6 levels of the 6-level model and can be translated to the A.U.T.O ontology. It includes object list-based trajectory information of road users and map information based on the Lanelet2 format. The format was developed from the Pegasus data format and the Common Data Format of the EU L3Pilot project and adapted to the needs of the urban use case. The most important feature is the availability of converters that enable the inclusion of data in a wide range of established formats in the scenario database.

Figure 30: Data flow through the OMEGA format within VVM

Thus, the methodology presented enables the complexity of real traffic to be translated into testable and simulatable logical scenario instances using a scenario concept and the functionalities of the scenario database.

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4.2.5 The concept of CORE-Scenarios and ODD-Metamodel

In addition to the aforementioned description levels (functional, logical, concrete) and description systematics (6-level model), another term is of central importance for the overall VVM method: the set of CORE-scenarios. These scenarios, figuratively, span the scenario space or cover the scenario space sufficiently completely. The analogy from mathematics is the set of UNIT VECTORS in linear

algebra, which span the vector space (e.g. R^n), or the Borel sets (*Borel -sigma Algebra*) in measure theory, which cover complex entities and thus make them measurable.

For a model of the ODD, we require a (small) set of (equivalence classes of) scenarios that represent the set of all scenarios in the ODD sufficiently completely, in addition to the abstraction level and description system.

The **set of CORE-scenarios** is defined as a set of representative classes of functional/logical scenarios. The set of CORE scenarios is defined as the smallest set of logical/functional scenarios that describe the known types of use cases that can occur in the ODD for the customer function as part of a secure and compliant behavior of the customer function within a secure and compliant ODD. Furthermore, the underlying base scenarios are disjointed. These scenarios define dynamic basic movement constellations. They represent the ODD sufficiently completely, and for each class, the smallest set of parameters has been declared that represents the known categories of parameters in each element of the set of logical scenarios that are relevant for the customer function in the ODD in the context of the logical scenarios. Furthermore, they are sorted according to relevance/exposure in the ODD.

The **ODD metamodel**, which is used in VVM, comprises a set of functional and logical core scenarios (classes/instances) and the scenario (parameter) database. The metamodel for ODD fulfills the requirement for decomposition of the scenario space regarding its use as a test space in the context of verification and validation.

The metamodel can be decomposed into CORE scenarios, which can themselves be decomposed into description levels. Each level of description can be decomposed into categories, and each category can be decomposed into parameters. The parameters of each scenario instance are defined within the context of the development process. The CORE scenarios are designed to create a model of the ODD. The basic scenarios are used to represent the ODD as completely as possible. This implies that this model can be employed consistently as a representative of the operating situations and states of the ODD. Figure 31 illustrates this. It can be demonstrated that the CORE scenarios represent a sufficiently complete model of the ODD (for further information, please refer to the methodological overview, the completeness section, or the completeness chapter).

Figure 31: Concept of core scenarios

The CORE scenarios can be formally described as ontology. VVM employs a formalized representation of the scenario model and links it with "knowledge" about the operating domain. This serves as the foundation for the A.U.T.O. ontology. In the context of the VVM overall method, an ontology is defined as a linguistically and formally organized representation of a set of concepts and their relationships within a domain. In the context of the VVM, the A.U.T.O. Ontology is employed. The integration of "knowledge about the domain," which arises from expert interviews and criticality analyses, among other sources, with the structures of the scenario model is a key aspect of this methodology. Data analyses are employed to identify criticality phenomena and interdependencies, which are subsequently formally linked to the A.U.T.O. ontology in a formal manner, with the description structures of the scenario model serving as the descriptive framework.

4.2.5.1 Why is a scenario-based ODD metamodel necessary?

As part of the established development process, scenarios are employed to formulate requirements, to design architectures, software, and hardware components, to verify and validate the functional safety concept, and to verify and validate the integrated overall system in the test process. PEGASUS has established scenario-based testing for automated driving systems, thereby integrating the scenario-based assessment of residual risk and the systematic, structured generation of test cases into the V&V process through the use of the 6-level scenario model.

Due to the necessity of employing scenarios in the various stages of development, different terminology and descriptions were often utilized in the different stages of development.

This, in addition to the resulting discrepancies in description and level of abstraction, presents a significant challenge

(1) in demonstrating that the models utilized are sufficiently representative of the operational design document (ODD). This entails demonstrating that the scenario classes employed, and the descriptive parameters utilized in the scenario adequately encompass the actual scenarios within the operational environment.

(2) in establishing a consistent, traceable, and verifiable process of requirements engineering, including its verification and validation.

(3) in demonstrating that the tests performed in the V&V and the field data analysis are based on the same semantic data model that was used to describe the scenario classes and properties during the problem analysis and system specification. (Hazards and dangerous situations that occur in the operational domain definition (ODD) were identified and are treated with an acceptable risk in the system design).

4.2.5.2 Outline of the approach regarding the completeness argumentation of the scenario concept

A comprehensive understanding of the operational domain (OD) is essential for the successful development of automated driving systems (ADSs). The understanding of the OD is expressed in the form of scenarios. The completeness of such scenarios depends on two factors: the completeness of the concept used to specify scenarios and the existence of scenarios that are like the OD. The objective of this section is to demonstrate how reasoning techniques can enhance the completeness of the scenario concept.

The completeness argumentation is divided into two stages: the argumentation of the consistency of the scenario concept and its completeness. Interestingly, the GSN strategies serve as the starting point for the completeness argument. This is because the absence of subgoals (goals that follow a strategy) renders a strategy invalid and therefore incomplete. Since we cannot know what is unknown, a counterargument is formulated that hypothetically questions the completeness of each strategy.

Typically, a hypothesis can either be accepted or rejected. In the case of an ADS, it can also be both, leading to a dilemma. The reasons for this can be unknown unknowns or an unspecified context. Both reasons can be addressed by utilizing the patterns that have been developed.

4.2.5.3 The role of the ODD metamodel in the safety case

The overall VVM method comprises two interrelated processes: the scenario process and the development and validation process. (See Figure 32) The ODD metamodel contributes to the derivation of requirements for the ADS, which is more comprehensive in terms of creating the prerequisites. This can enhance the robustness of the ADS against hazards and dangerous situations in the intended area of use with its specific operating conditions by systematically searching for and integrating CORE scenarios and ODD or scenario features that were not previously considered in the ODD metamodel.

Figure 32: Interrelation between the scenario process and the development and validation process

Reference:

Glasmacher, Weber, Eckstein, Towards a Completeness Argumentation for Scenario Concepts, 2024

4.2.5.4 One fits for all - a scenario-based Meta-Model for the ODD used consistently in the Development Process of an ADS.

For the implementation of scenario-based testing / verification in simulation or on proving grounds, it is necessary that requirements defining system behavior or limits can be evaluated in parameter spaces with sampling methods. A structured model of the ODD is needed for this purpose. In PEGASUS, the scenario description was developed in the form of the 6-layer model and by abstraction levels functional, logical, concrete.

The 6-layer model was extended in VVM by the use case "city". The concept of "logical scenario model" was extended to include the terms logical scenario "class" and "instance". A logical scenario class is created when the relevant parameters (for the customer function and the associated ODD of the ADS to be developed) have been defined, i.e., declared. This becomes an instance when the parameters of the class have value ranges defined or instantiated. The details of this procedure can be found in Figure 33.

Figure 33: Procedure of creating logical scenario instances

The result of this process is a set of CORE scenarios (functional or logical in the form of instances) that represent a sufficiently complete metamodel of the ODD and a scenario database that has been representatively fed with data so that it serves as a tool for deriving exposure. The metamodel for ODD supports the requirement for decomposition:

- metamodel is decomposable into CORE scenarios.
- each layer of a CORE scenario is decomposable
- each parameter in a layer is decomposable

4.2.6 Things to add to the design and V&V process

One of the basic ideas of the overall approach is "thinking from the end / artefact needed to argue". The ODD meta model is added, while it allows to perform "OD-Domain analysis & System Design & Safeguarding of the System" on the same set of scenarios representing validly the ODD. The OD-Domain analysis is added, while it gives a deep understanding of the problem space and is basis for the SOTIF hazard and risk analysis and definition of safety goals as well as for the

integration of stakeholder needs (legal, society, ethical, ...) in the system behavior and/or design. The Risk management Core (RMC) is added while; it defines a process framework for managing risk especially in the context of specifying system behavior and handling hazardous events.

4.2.6.1 OD-Domain Analysis

In the 'System Specification' step, a rigorous and systematic analysis is performed for the ODD, the driving automation (risk) and the customer function, which together represent the problem space. This "knowledge of the problem space" is used to methodically identify occurrence of hazardous and triggering events in the set of CORE scenarios from the metamodel of the ODD. This includes a systematic hazard and risk analysis and identification of hazard events, which not only involves the consideration of a failure of the automated driving function, but also a systematic consideration of inherent hazardous conditions or events triggering them within the interaction between the system vehicle and its environment (described scenario-based by the meta-model of the ODD), which must be avoided.

Methods for analyzing the problem space and identifying relevant phenomena are, e.g., the analysis of existing knowledge and expert know-how, including analysis of accident databases and field data. Another example is expert analysis, called "criticality analysis" throughout. Classes of scenarios in which the system should operate are defined and analyzed to identify the dominant characteristics of the environment. A key challenge in ensuring the safety of highly automated driving is to provide sufficient confidence that all possible systematic triggering or hazardous events are known and controlled at the time the system is released in its ODD.

The overall VVM approach therefore integrates "risk analysis", "risk assessment", and "risk treatment", and complements these topics with the process-related management of "residual risk", which must be kept below an acceptable level for ADS to be considered safe. The process-related required risk reduction determines the extent of the measures taken to reduce the severity or probability of damage to the defined acceptable residual risk. The scenario catalog for which the actual risk of the system must be managed is the ODD metamodel (set of CORE scenarios). The functional behavior of automated driving functions is typically described by defining their behavior in use and non-use cases. Based on core scenarios from the ODD metamodel, the functional description of the system can therefore be defined in terms of a set of functional use cases that define the intended functional behavior, a functional domain, and the specification of boundaries. Scenarios are well suited for describing test cases by extending the scenario descriptions with pass/fail criteria.

A first improvement of the customer function defined by use cases is the integration of a set of requirements that represent the stakeholder needs as legal, societal, ethical, but also driving style expectations on the intended behavior of the system in the CORE scenarios. These requirements must be defined in a traceable way and have a clear definition of the boundaries of the system's behavior with respect to these constraints.

In this context, it is necessary to establish a traceable process within the design of an ADS that balances the sometimes situationally conflicting requirements resulting from driving style, legal, social, ethical, and liability requirements, among others. This process should determine the resulting risks and, in the case of deviations due to individual necessary decisions, make the resulting additional risk transparent for the manufacturer.

The traceability from stakeholder needs to target behavior specification is exemplarily supported by the Semantic Norm Behavior Analysis and the Phenomenon-Signal Model, the traceability from the behavior specification to the system design by a structured specification of system capabilities.

The ODD metamodel is added, allowing "Validation & Verification on the same ODD metamodel as Hazard and Risk Analysis and System Design". This results in the new V&V task of validating the sufficient validity of the current set of CORE scenarios, i.e., evidence must be provided validating that the CORE scenario and associated properties provide adequate coverage of the real scenarios encountered in the target domain.

The evaluation of the risk managed system [safety] behavior is added, while it is essential to prove that the system behaves safely or that the risk acceptance criteria are met in its ODD.

The V&V concept gets a focus on an assurance related organization of V&V. Hence, test objects, test objectives, test levels, test platforms and test strategies are linked by the V&V concept and aligned with the need for artifacts and evidence of building the safety assurance argument.

Verification - Objective Max. possible coverage of "sensitive" areas concerning potential severity of consequences, exposure & controllability.

Concept for "sensitive" areas and test cases

- ▶ Decomposition of ODD (generation of scenario instances) based on e.g. "criticality analysis" combined with probabilistic analyses.
- ▶ Analysis of relevant design elements with respect to its attribution towards safety.
- ▶ Composition of "sensitive" areas by the merge of relevant design- and scenario characteristics.
- ▶ Generation of test cases from attribution of design and ODD analysis.

Validation - Objective Estimation of the residual risks (after verification) with statistical methods e.g. using near misses. Strategy: Random ODD selection and confirmation of diversity.

Concept for risk estimation and feasibility

- ▶ The residual risk is determined by statistical descriptions of the probability of occurrence of hazardous behavior or risks including significance level.
- ▶ Feasibility is achieved by iterative feedback loops into the development process e.g. when relevant unknowns are found.
- ▶ Risk thresholds are determined by correspondence to the required safety level.

4.2.7 Scenario-based verification

The purpose of scenario-based verification in the overall VVM methodology is requirements-based testing or testing the implemented behavior against the ADS specification. The behavior could be verified by scenario-based testing based on the ODD metamodel and its related parameter spaces. Verification demonstrates, by providing objective evidence (i.e., testing and evaluation), that the specified requirements for the product are met. When the functionality is confirmed, it is ensured that all the functions and safety mechanisms that are relevant to safety are free from critical faults. System verification focuses on determining the (robust) performance of the ADS with respect to

known triggering events. It evaluates that the residual risk associated with hazardous events caused by known insufficiencies is sufficiently low.

4.2.7.1 Verification concept

The Verification concept defines the approach of verifying of the system operations and the proof of the correct implementation of all requirements and specifications.

It defines what will be tested (test objectives), the purposes for which the test is intended to provide evidence of achievement (Test Goals), the levels to which different system elements will be tested (Test Levels), includes general test strategies for “requirement-based” testing, the test environments (Test Platforms) used and a test matrix with detailed mapping connecting the testing performed to the system requirements. Furthermore, it is conformed to the norm ISO 26262 and ISO 21448. Testing is the systematic, coverage-oriented, structured and methodical execution of tests defined by test case specifications.

4.2.7.2 Enhancements in verification

The system and its components (sensors, algorithms and actuators) are verified in order to show that they behave as expected in their ODD especially in known / unsafe scenarios and are sufficiently covered by the tests performed.

Furthermore, it must be proven that the system and its components do not contain any undesired functionality or show operation characteristics which might violate safety objectives in its ODD. In the context of verification of the automated driving functionality, well established global test objectives including correct "functionality", "performance" achievement and detection of "system limits/ODD boundaries" can be verified by scenario-based testing using the metamodel for the ODD. The method "analysis of scenario spaces" can be used to derive concrete tests (Figure 34).

Figure 34: Details of the V-model including aspects of scenario-based testing

4.2.8 Scenario-based Validation

The purpose of scenario-based validation in the overall VVM method is distance-based testing with endurance runs or field-based tests under non-deterministic / stochastic conditions in real work traffic on public roads. So, an overall task is uncovering “unknown/unknown” and “incomplete specifications or implementations” and “unintended behavior”. Validation has the purpose to prove that the demands to safety and performance of the ADS, its safe handling of all possible (traffic) scenarios, as well as satisfaction and acceptance by customers. It is also used for testing all characteristics of scenarios that cannot be tested in simulation or that cannot be performed on proving ground. Hence the accurate detection of ODD boundaries and activation of the system only within the ODD is proved here. This also includes checking compliance with traffic rules respectively behavioral law. The data is also evaluated with criticality metrics providing an assessment of potential safety risks and compliant behavior.

4.3 The Risk Management Perspective

4.3.1 Risk management (Core)

The idea of consistent use of controlled and managed risk throughout the design and safeguarding. The so-called "Risk Management Core" (RMC) is proposed as a process tool for risk management in automated driving. The Risk Management Core is an iterative process to align the actual risk with the accepted risk. The RMC supports an explicit representation and treatment of risks in hazardous or triggering events contained in scenarios that cause hazardous behavior.

The Challenge: Safe Automated Driving Systems

Homologation of AD systems requires to fulfill societal safety expectations. Multiple Hazards are present at the same time, identified from different sources e.g. behavior, technology, norms like ISO 26262 and ISO 21448.

The Solution: Risk Management Core (RMC)

The Risk Management Core is an iterative process to align actual risk with accepted risk. It supports an explicit representation and treatment of risks:

- Risk as leading measure for safety
- Aggregation of all system risk aspects with “Risk-modeling” -approach
- Alignment of system risk with Risk Acceptance Criteria in an iterative loop

Inputs for the Risk Management Core (RMC)

- Hazards
- Situations / Scenarios
- Risk Acceptance Criteria

Outputs of the Risk Management Core (RMC)

- Safety Goals

- Risk based decisions
- Risk reduction measures together with target values
- Aggregated risk aspects for Safety Argumentation
- The outputs fulfill current norm requirements and support industrial engineering processes.

Figure 35: Risk Management Core with Advantages

4.3.1.1 Advantages of the Risk Management Core (RMC)

In this section, the advantages of the RMC as depicted in the blue boxes in Figure 35 will be described in detail:

Consideration of All Kind of Hazard Sources

The RMC considers all kinds of hazards in one approach. Hazards may be identified from sources such as ISO 26262 Functional Safety or ISO 21448 SOTIF. Hazards can come even from outside the ADS equipped vehicle, e.g., from unexpected or unlawful behavior of other traffic participants, from animals crossing or even from stone throwers on bridges. The RMC stores all identified hazards in a hazard log.

Simple Overall Structure

The RMC is rather simple structured in 5 areas:

1. Risk Analysis - Analysis the hazards and estimate the risks
2. Risk Modeling - Attach multiple risks to multiple risk acceptance criteria and bring multiple risks in relation to each other.
3. Risk Acceptance - Establish the criteria for unreasonable risk

4. Risk Evaluation - Evaluate whether the risk emerging from the system is below the accepted risk
5. Risk Treatment - Define and check the safety measures

Multiple stakeholders have the same view.

Consideration of Multiple Risks at a Time

In contrast to just failure considerations, in real-world context we need to consider multiple risks at the same time.

For example, when overtaking a bicycle under a bridge with pillars between the lanes, we need to consider risks from two different hazards in parallel: "collision of the ADS equipped vehicle with a bridge pillar potentially causing injury of the driver and passengers" in parallel with "collision between the ADS equipped vehicle and bicyclist potentially causing injury of the bicyclist".

Integration of Existing Safety Standards

The RMC is based on a set of existing safety standards such as ISO Guide 51, ISO 26262, ISO 21448, ISO/TR 4804, ISO/TS 5083.

That is, applying the RMC is not an additional task but in contrast fulfills requirements from standards that need to be applied anyway.

Weighing Up the Risks

Consideration of multiple risks at the same time means that

- Risks are represented in relation to each other. Ideally in a numeric way.
For example, collision hazards are dependent on distances to the collision objects. In this case, a path with minimal risk could be calculated.
- Each risk (or collection of risks) needs to be connected to at least one risk acceptance criterion
Note: Risks or Risk collections may be connected to more than one risk acceptance criterion

Handle Societal Safety Expectations

The concept of risk acceptance criteria (RAC) includes the opportunity to handle societal safety expectations.

RAC formulated by entities representing the society - such as authorities - can be interpreted as societal safety expectations.

Explicit Comparison of "Actual Risk" versus "Accepted Risk"

The explicit comparison of "actual risks" versus "accepted risks" allows the achievement of "absence of unreasonable risk" while generating solid evidence for the safety argumentation.
Note 1: Risk can be measured in units like "harm per time", „harm per event". But also, with other units based on parameters that have a relation to harm and probability (and usually also to time).
Note 2: It is important that the measure unit of the accepted risk / risk acceptance criterion is from the same type as the "actual risk" measured/estimated for the system.

Evaluation of risk in RMC

To reconcile actual and accepted risk, it is necessary to establish risk acceptance criteria that apply to ODD. In 2017, the German Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure commissioned a report on the ethical considerations of automated driving. One of the recommendations was that it must be demonstrated that the automated driving systems are on average better than a human driver in terms of avoidance or mitigation of hazardous situations, although in some cases it may be acceptable for performance to be slightly worse than a human as long as an overall "positive risk balance" is achieved. A related approach, based on the French definition "Globalement au moins aussi bon", refers to the principle that any new system must be at least as good as any previous system it replaces.

PEGASUS used both to propose as risk acceptance criteria: a positive risk balance or a performance of the system in avoiding an accident of severity S1 - S3 must be at least 50% of human performance. The VVM method adopts this and uses the same risk assessment in RMC and Validation & Verification.

Derive target behavior of the automated driving system based on an acceptable risk

The identification of hazardous target behaviors is supported by a risk-based refinement of functional specification by matching it to the previously identified hazards. Functional deficiencies are presented to explicitly address them with risk mitigation measures (qualitative and quantitative). If the level of risk posed by the identified hazardous target behavior is unacceptable, safety goals are defined that capture the required qualitative and quantitative risk reduction and safety measures are derived from them. If the measures for the target behavior are acceptable and feasible, a first iteration loop using the RMC refines the functional target behavior on a risk basis. The first iteration loop is completed by integrating the specified risk reduction measures into the behavior specification, which is followed by another risk analysis of the target behavior. If this first iteration step derives or requires measures that cannot be implemented in the context of target behavior adjustments, alternative mitigation measures are defined that are suitable for achieving the safety goal (e.g., adjusting the ODD by defining adjusted system boundaries).

After the first iteration loop has adjusted the target behavior and any derived safety goals and measures in the behavior specification so that the residual risk from the target behavior of the system of interest is acceptable, a second iteration loop begins. Now, triggering conditions that may lead to deviations from the target behavior are analyzed in the same way. If the deviations turn out to be hazardous, the risk resulting from such a behavior has to be quantified in terms of probability of occurrence and severity. To pass iteration 2, the risk from the target behavior must be below the acceptable risk level. Further risk reduction through risk-based adjustments to the target behavior is required if the risk assessment indicates that the risk acceptability criterion is violated. Risks arising from the specified safety mechanisms are necessarily reanalyzed in Iteration 1. A refined behavior specification can be created when all risk acceptance criteria are met by the behavior specification, including risk mitigation and safety integrity. At the end it must be verified that the specified behavior is an exact representation of the intended and in SW implemented behavior.

Scenarios allow the explicit involvement of experts in the iterative development process.

Explicit Value for Risk Reduction Need

As the RMC uses explicit risk values, it can generate an explicit value for the risk reduction need: A positive value of "actual risk - accepted risk" is the value for the "necessary risk reduction". A negative value means that there is evidence for the "absence of unreasonable risk", that is the risk is sufficiently low.

Separated Values for "Risk Reduction Need" and "Integrity"

The value of the "necessary risk reduction" is attached to the according safety goal as a value separated from the integrity requirements like ASIL.

This allows seamless integration with established approaches for functional safety, that uses classification for the (integrity) safety measures rather than explicit risks values

Note 1: Integrity requirements and the "nominal risk reduction need" are dependent. Low integrity requirements usually lead to higher values for the nominal risk reduction.

Note 2: In ADS applications the value for nominal risk reduction need usually represents the major share of risk compared to the risk variance addressed by integrity requirements.

Explicit Risk Reduction Measures:

Based on the values for integrity requirements and the risk reduction need, different measures need to be defined:

- Safety measures, that reduce the risks the system induces to driver, passengers and environment mainly based on its existence and on its behavior.
- Safety measures that minimize the risk stemming from system failures according to the integrity requirements
- (Other) safety measures to eliminate hazards or reduce risks, e.g by limiting the operational design domain

Safety measures need to be defined for all hazards where the according risk(s) exceeds the accepted risk.

Note: There are measures that can address both integrity requirements and nominal risk reduction (e.g. process measures)

Closed Risk-Control Loop: Check Effectiveness

One main advantage of the RMC is the closed loop, that aligns "actual risks" with "accepted risks" to design and to argue for a safe system.

This closed loop is created by checking the effectiveness of the introduced safety measures. The measures either have an effect on the severity or on the probability of a hazard. By re-estimating the actual system risk with the implemented measures, the RMC generates evidence that the defined measures actually reduce the actual risk sufficiently to be below the accepted risk.

4.3.1.2 Application of the RMC for multiple purposes

While the Risk Management Core collects all the hazards and safety goals of the whole product, it is still applied for different dedicated tasks, e.g.

- Creation of safe target behavior
- Alignment of system risks with acceptance criteria
- Risk Estimation of specific system elements
- Risk Evaluation at start of production

4.3.1.3 Interface to the Safety Argumentation (optional)

The RMC supports arguments

- for risks having specific values,
- for risk acceptance criteria to be well selected and sufficiently considered,
- for measures sufficiently reducing risks,
- for the residual risk to be sufficiently low and
- for risks and acceptance criteria as to why they can be combined.

References:

N. F. Salem et al., "Risk Management Core -- Towards an Explicit Representation of Risk in Automated Driving." arXiv, Feb. 15, 2023. doi: [10.48550/arXiv:2302.07715](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv:2302.07715)

[VVM Final Event POSTER 3.7 - Risk Management Core](#)

4.4 The Safety Argumentation Perspective

4.4.1 probFMEA and CFT in the new assurance framework

Since the probFMEA/CFT method was already described in deliverable D03 it will be addressed in D11, how this method attributes to the process of deriving test requirements. In Figure 37 it can be seen how the probFMEA / CFT is integrated into the assurance framework.

Figure 36: Integration of the probFMEA / CFT method in the assurance framework

Essential for performing the analysis with probFMEA / CFT are the functional and technical specifications that are available within the context of the functional and technical architecture or design definition. One result can be an initial appraisal of the risk that occurs. Based on the methodology, test cases can be identified that have not yet been covered by tests. The methodology does not generate new test cases per se but can help uncover testing white spots and help test planning achieve more complete test coverage. Criteria and methods for testing can be recommended in consultation with the test planning. One useful tool to achieve better test coverage is the Minimal Cut Set analysis that helps to unveil critical weaknesses and triggering conditions.

With the input of the methodology, targeted tests can be planned by test planning and test orchestration to test specific failure modes identified based on the probFMEA / CFT analysis. To iteratively improve failure analysis, insight into test results and a prediction of test coverage is valuable. Identifying critical weaknesses and their triggering conditions and pointing out where there is a need for improvement can help to achieve an optimization of the design.

4.4.2 Model-based safety analysis with safeTbox and Genie

One tool to enable a model-based safety analysis is safeTbox (<https://www.safetbox.de>). safeTBox is a plugin to Enterprise Architect enables the direct integration of system architectures. It focusses on architecture integration, traceability, reusability, and maintainability of safety-relevant artifacts.

The key features of safeTbox are Architecture Design, Hazard and Risk analysis, Fault Analysis and Safety Argumentation via Goal Structuring Notation.

In our work, safeTbox has been extended by dedicated means to support safety-of-the-intended-function (SOTIF) aspects. The following typed basic events have been introduced to support the modelling:

- Weakness: Insufficiency or incapability of a sensor or sensor processing
- Triggering Condition: The potential reason for triggering a weakness
- Triggered Weakness: Intermediate event representing a system failure
- Failure of measure: Event that represents a not properly addressed triggered weakness

Typed events allow automatic checks for consistency in modelling. Furthermore, due to component-reuse it is possible to reuse knowledge about weaknesses and triggering conditions of sensors and processing. Furthermore, types provide additional information to meaningfully interpret results of safety analysis.

Figure 37: Failure propagation including SOTIF aspects modelled with safeTbox

The modeling steps to be applied for the safety analysis are:

Step 1: Model hierarchical capabilities

Dependences between the capabilities are modelled as ports, using this structure as input for the failure propagation model aligned with the architecture. (Figure 38)

Figure 38: Step 1 - Modelling with capabilities

Step 2: Modelling of failure propagation based on the dependencies

Analysis starts with a top-level element. Causes for the violations are tracked down using the modelled dependencies to the atomic element of the analyzed abstraction level. Application of keywords at the level of dependencies and events to enable systematic identification of failure causes. (Figure 40)

Figure 39: Step 2 - Failure propagation

Step 3: Modelling failure causes considering quality measurements and w.r.t. SOTIF

Influence of used technologies to specific use case is modelled as well as violations of required quality measurements. (Figure 40)

Figure 40: Step 3 - Failure causes with quality measures

Step 4: Qualitative Analysis with Minimal Cut Sets Safety Analysis is used to identify Triggering Conditions for testing and Triggered Weaknesses with no/insufficient counter measures.

Evidence of safety and robustness is supported by considering the Minimal Cut Set order and the probability of safety goal violation from Bayesian Network inference. This enables an automated aggregation of risk analysis results. (Figure 41)

Figure 41: Step 4 - Bayesian Network of the subsystem "object detection at right side" based on the component fault tree in SafeTbox

Evidence of safety and robustness is supported by considering the Minimal Cut Set order and the probability of safety goal violation from Bayesian Network inference. This enables an automated aggregation of risk analysis results. To ensure a seamless integration of SafeTbox and Bayesian Networks it was demonstrated VVM how an interface between these tools could look like. In Figure 42 it is shown how a Bayesian Network is structured. An automated generation of the networks is not yet possible, and research is still needed to enable seamless integration.

5 Conclusions, recommendations and future perspectives

The VVM overall method combines the perspectives of **scenario-based testing**, **safety-by-design** and **risk management** with the approach of a **systematic argumentation** in order to develop **safety assured mobility systems** whereby safety can be **explained to society**. Key to mastering complexity is given by consequent **separation of perspectives** and their **seamless interaction** by clearly defined links as well as effective integration of established automotive processes.

The following thematic pathways are considered as further enabler for scenario-based safety verification and validation to the next level.

5.1 Outlook: Scenario-based testing and virtualization

5.1.1 Upscaling critical scenarios

While it can be justified to assume there being only a finite and manageable number of safety-critical factors to consider, testing all their possible combinations still leads to a combinatorial explosion easily exceeding any realistic testing budget. While scenario-based testing delivers promising results, in practice, ODDs are ever-increasing. In this case, practical applicability of scenario-based testing is directly related to the ability of incorporating these individually improbable but collectively relevant edge cases methodically into safety cases. Hence, how do we efficiently generate evidence, e.g., as test data, for system safety in these scenarios? A specific research approach dedicated to critical scenario generation anticipating edge cases covering the increasing ODD space may be a relevant and necessary answer to upscaled automated driving deployment.

5.1.2 Application of ODD modeling

The structuring of the Operational Domain and the Operational Design Domain as initiated by PEGASUS and VV Methods needs to be enhanced with description languages for the ODD, especially for simulation use cases. For many applications of L4 automated driving, it would also be highly relevant to have improved on-board algorithms available whether the vehicle is still inside its ODD. Approaches concerning the usage of core scenarios for a database of safe scenarios and the combination of these “atoms” for larger ODDs combined from stored standard pieces need to be investigated further, especially in case the Core Scenarios do not only cover geometric descriptions like “straight-road” or “t-shaped junction” or a “roundabout” structure. This is especially important in case traffic- and/or weather-related effects come into play which might affect the safe operation of an ADS in a given traffic area that would be considered “safe” under standard conditions.

5.1.3 Reality abstraction, virtual environments and corresponding tooling

Systematic approaches transferring the reality into versatile virtual elements s.a. models, complementary datasets mixing real and virtual data as well as the corresponding and harmonized virtual test facilities are necessary for large scale application of the VVM scenario-based testing methodology. While current abstraction processes are more-or-less based on data-driven reality abstraction in selected pilots, new (and scalable) model-based procedures calibrating and validating the models could launch the next step in applying scenario-based testing methodologies to industrial use.

Virtual environments play a crucial role in verification and validation (V&V), particularly when considering simulation as a service. The effective integration of diverse test facilities and environments, such as virtual environments, Hardware-in-the-Loop (HiL)/Vehicle-in-the-Loop (ViL), proving grounds, and field tests, is essential to accumulate comprehensive evidence.

5.1.4 Innovative data- and data-service ecosystems

Virtual safety assurance linking high-quality and traceable data and data services (partly based on open data, synthetic (AI-based) data, abstract test and pilot site elements) with industrial R&D and V&V processes is required to fulfill all requirements of safety case methodologies. Innovative ecosystems e.g. as currently are provided by several open marketplaces require to be linked to continuous data- and scenario pipelines with at least TRL 7 maturity. One specific example would concern the continuous updating of high-definition maps and equipping these with the urgently needed information about sensor-relevant material data (e.g., reflection and refraction properties for radar and lidar). Such continuous integration chains are needed to reach the required levels of quality of the whole data supply chain for verification and validation

5.1.5 Updated and harmonized scenario DBs

Scenario-based testing methods as initialized by the PEGASUS family projects have stimulated the development of several scenario database projects and even first scenario marketplaces designed especially for the safety case. These scenario databases, to some extent, are already harmonized by the corresponding standardization activities e.g. process views by ISO and technical specifications by ASAM and others. With the finalization of relevant standards for scenario-based testing in 2024 and the existing 2022 regulations in Europe, new scenario DB harmonization efforts may be necessary to support the intended deployment of automated driving.

Such a database could be governed by an independent body and structured similarly to the German GIDAS accident database and should include logical scenarios and the required parameter types as well as bandwidths for the parameter and additional metrics. Such a database has to combine existing scenario DBs, updated with the recent results from the initiatives mentioned above and has to integrate all relevant stakeholder needs from industry, regulation and academia.

5.2 Outlook: Risk Handling and safety case application

5.2.1 Application of risk modeling

Within VV Methods, we developed a process framework with the goal of explicit representation and management of risk – the Risk Management Core. The conceptual framework is based on existing safety standards and applied to the specific challenge of refining a behavior specification of an Automated Driving System. While we illustrated this application of the Risk Management Core in a research publication³, there are open questions regarding further applications of the framework. Especially, the application of the “risk modeling” step within the Risk Management Core holds multiple challenges. For example, methods are needed to aggregate estimated risks from multiple scenarios to an estimation at the ODD-level. Additionally, risk acceptance criteria will need to be applied both at the ODD-level as well as at the scenario-specific level.

5.2.2 The role of risk management for Security / Cybersecurity

The different safety requirements as well as the effects of the respective risk-reducing measures have a differentiated effect on the risk posed by the vehicle. In the Risk Management Core, an essential element of the VVM method, the abstract semantic requirements are merged and compared with the requirement classes and its labels. Here, for example, risks from functional safety and SOTIF can be combined. Therefore, requirements of security/cybersecurity can be merged and evaluated with this approach in the same way. However, it is essential that the risks from safety and security are aggregated in common consideration. Accordingly, conflicts of objectives of safety and security measures must also be clarified via further rule sets (usually by including an extended context).

5.2.3 Applying the safety case on concrete ODDs

Safety-by-design based on virtual elements comes with very high demands on modeling procedures, data quality and traceability, systems engineering approaches for test orchestration and interoperability of all involved elements. “Elements” also means modeling uncertainties. Uncertainties should be quantified to improve the process of V&V as well as to improve the safety of AD. Handling uncertainties is key to enable industrialization of AD and even of SAE L2 functions. Systematic national and multi-national approaches to how to transfer scenario-based testing methodologies based on uncertainties into industrial application stimulates the required transformation from scientific into industrial processes. At the same time this transformation effort incorporates all and maybe new relevant actors enables would serve as a linking element between existing testing capacities and facilities.

³ N. F. Salem u. a., „Risk Management Core – Towards an Explicit Representation of Risk in Automated Driving“, IEEE Access, 2024, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3372860.

5.3 Outlook: Technological Challenges

5.3.1 Explicit Specification of Target Behavior

ISO 21448 provides initial guidelines for the specification of safe intended behavior an Automated Driving System shall exhibit in its context. However, there are no methods referenced by the standard that can be applied in an industrial setting. Thus, VV Methods proposed approaches to generate a behavior specification that can be used to support safety analyses in the context of SOTIF (but also in the context of functional safety according to ISO 26262). While these approaches were applied in a limited scope of example scenarios, further investigation is necessary how the proposed methods perform in larger scale settings. Additionally, the interrelation between behavior specification and technical design was considered conceptually as VV Methods did not focus on technical design. Future work could focus on how a behavior specification can support a traceable specification of technical requirements.

5.3.2 The role of AI in the safety case

How do future AI-elements s.a. training data, virtually generated data, models and Ai-generated functionalities as well as AI-based decision algorithms correspond to the overall safety case and how can they be integrated in the safety case?

In principle, each relevant AI-system element in terms of a functional chain of effects is included in the VVM overall method with regards to its influence on safety (in the same way as classic elements). Within the overall method each element, whether classic-design or AI-design, must provide its systemic reference to function, risk, data and their reasoning in an argumentation. The AI-specific handling is well described via the focus areas of ISO PAS 8800:

- AI lifecycle processes as e.g. new data lifecycle
- AI safety requirements and AI safety measures such as e.g. new safety analyses and new data and model safety properties.
- Safe AI development & evaluation as e.g. new AI safety analysis or field operation monitoring

The challenge of and the key path for integration of AI-elements into the safety case argumentation lies in the comparability of its performance-metrics and AI-safety methods.

5.3.3 Concern management

In VVM the term concern management was assigned to the handling of “cross-cutting concerns”, whereby “cross-cutting concern” in terms of VVM signifies aspects or phenomena that have a relevant influence on claims or top goals, usually on safety and performance of the system, but their effects or causes cannot be separated arbitrarily far or there is a significant uncertainty about this. Therefore, within the framework the cross-cutting concern needs to be coordinated between different domains. Cross-cutting concerns can originate from technical nature such as the influence of the shaking of a camera on the recognition quality, for example due to potholes (technical emergencies). Cross-cutting concerns can also arise at the requirements level, such as conflicts upcoming from safety and security requirements contradictions.

The VVM concept of concern-management is an assignment of cross-cutting concerns towards a proprietary cross-domain structure (e.g. data-structures), which links known influence of cross-cutting concerns to the different domains, such the influence of solar-glare (aspect of ODD domain) towards the testing of optical sensors (aspect of V&V domain). Concern-management thus supplements the interfaces between meta-layers, domains and their hierarchies with a store of cross-domain development challenges or problem spaces. The aim of these structures is not to create parallelism but to store knowledge and later analyze and develop the cross-cutting concerns to the extent that their influences can be transferred to measures in the domains and their interfaces until the risks they are posing is sufficiently limited. Concerns are also addressed by the argumentation structure. The concerns of argumentation comprise the impact of the cross-cutting concerns and general concerns of argumentation.

5.3.4 Remote Operation

Remote operation as a bridge technology between human-driven vehicles and full automation could imply its own validation & verification challenges that consequentially have to be handled by scenario-based testing methodologies. In contrast to the scope of VVM, the involvement of a human driver and in particular the connectivity between vehicle and tele-operation infrastructure needs to be addressed. In case of a loss or severe degradation of connectivity, a minimum risk maneuver would need to be executed autonomously via on-board systems. In addition, the maximum driving times of a remote operator and that impact on his/her capabilities as well as the effects of round-trip latency from the vehicle to the tele-operation center and back (including human reaction times) need to be evaluated. Many tools proposed in VVM could be used for this analysis, like the ODD meta model, the ontology approaches, data formats, scenario data bases, and the proposed test methods like Adaptive Replay-to-Sim, and Vehicle/Prototype-in-the-Loop.

5.3.5 Collective learning and adjustment concepts from in-field operations

Currently, in-field testing or operation of automated driving systems is accelerated and conducted in various countries. A systematic sharing of non-proprietary data and knowledge gained in these activities can drastically reduce the efforts of all parties involved and can thus act as a catalyst for improvements. Ideally, this leads to increased safety even before systems enter field tests, as parties have the possibility to access safety-relevant factors and their underlying causalities for their target ODD. How to collectively learn from field data? Here, an open and system-independent knowledge base and its according specifications in-line with the latest standardization parameters and metrics are a valuable tool. A cross-country systems-engineering approach collecting, evaluating and transferring relevant data and experiences into the safety case as well as into the product development driven value chains is a promising approach to increase safety and reduce efforts.